

Hybrid Approach for Numerical Optimization using an Enhanced Sand Cat Swarm Algorithm

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Abstract:

This study introduces a hybridization algorithm called Sand Cat Swarm Optimization (SCSO), which mimics the survival behaviors of sand cats in nature. The two types of phases are search and attack. The SCSO was tested in MATLAB 2023a using functions F1 to F23, and the results were compared with those of other effective hybridization algorithms. SCSO achieved the best solution of -3.39 for function F19 among the test functions. The improved results indicate that SCSO excels in convergence rate and effectively locates most, if not all, local and global optima, outperforming the other methods in comparison.

Keywords: Benchmark, Optimization, Hybridization, PSO, SCSO.

Introduction:

In everyday life, optimization involves reducing time and costs while increasing efficiency and quality. Heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms are two types used to find optimized solutions [1]. Heuristic algorithms are tailored to specific problems, while metaheuristic algorithms are more general and do not rely on a particular challenge they find optimal solutions through a random search within predefined boundaries. When solving an optimization challenge, it is important to define the relevant variable values according to the specific problem at hand [2]. The sand cat (*Felis margarita*) is a member of the *Felis* genus, which is part of the mammal family.

This species thrives in harsh environments, such as sandy and stony deserts found in regions like Central Asia, the Sahara, and the Arabian Peninsula. The small, agile sand cat exhibits unique hunting and living behaviors that differ from those of domestic cats, despite their similar appearance [3]. Unlike many other felines, sand cats are solitary animals. Their paws and foot soles are covered with a dense layer of fur that ranges from sandy to light grey, providing insulation against the extreme temperatures of the desert [4].

Literature Review:

The Sand Cat Swarm Optimization (SCSO) algorithm is based on the behaviors of sand cats in the wild. Sand cats primarily engage in two activities: hunting for prey and attacking it [5]. This remarkable feature allows them to locate prey, whether it's on the surface or underground, enabling them to catch it quickly. Since sand cats are solitary animals in their natural habitat, the authors of the proposed algorithm treated them as a group to highlight the idea of swarm intelligence [6]. Therefore, during the initialization of the algorithm, the number of sand cats can be set to optimize either a minimization or maximization problem. There 4 types of classification there are Evolutionary-Based, Human-Inspired, Natural-Inspired, Physical-Based Algorithms [7].

1. Evolutionary-Based Algorithms:

These are algorithms that are based on biological evolution, especially the ideas of natural selection and the concept of survival of the fittest.

2. Human-Inspired Algorithms:

These methods are based on human intelligence, behaviors, and decision-making strategies.

3. Natural-Inspired Algorithms:

These are algorithms that take cues from natural processes and phenomena. They often imitate the behaviors of living organisms and ecosystems to tackle optimization challenges.

4. Physical-Based Algorithms:

These algorithms that physical laws, forces, and mathematical models such as gravity, electromagnetism, and wave dynamics.

Fig-1: Classification of nature-inspired algorithms

Pseudocode:

1. Initialize the population of sand cats randomly within the search space.
2. Set maximum number of iterations and define the objective function.
3. Initialize velocity (for PSO) for each sand cat.
4. Evaluate fitness of each sand cat.
5. Identify the best-performing sand cat (global best solution).
6. Update velocity of sand cats using PSO velocity equations:

$$v_i = w \cdot v_i + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (p_{best} - x_i) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (g_{best} - x_i)$$

- Update the positions of sand cats using a combination of:
- SCSO Exploration: Random movement in the environment.
- SCSO Exploitation: Moving toward the best solution.
- PSO-inspired velocity-driven movement: Updating positions using velocity.
 $x_i = x_i + v_i$
- Evaluate the new fitness values.
- Update the best solution if a better one is found.
- Store the convergence curve (Best Fitness per iteration).

7. Return the best solution and the convergence curve.

Table1: Benchmark Functions

Table 2: Standard UM benchmark functions

Functions	Dimensions	Range	f_{min}
$F_1(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z S_m^2$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0
$F_2(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z S_m + \prod_{m=1}^z S_m $	(10,30,50,100)	[-10, 10]	0
$F_3(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z (\sum_{n=1}^m S_n)^2$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0
$F_4(S) = \max_m S_m , 1 \leq m \leq z$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0

$F_5(S) = \sum_{m=1}^{z-1} [100(S_{m+1}S_m^2)^2 + (S_m - 1)^2]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-38, 38]	0
$F_6(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z ((S_m + 0.5))^2$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0
$F_7(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z mS_m^4 + random [0,1]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-1.28, 1.28]	0

Functions	Dimension	Range	f_{min}
$F_8(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z S_m - S_m \sin(\sqrt{ S_m })$	(10,30,50,100)	[-500,500]	-418.98295
$F_9(S) = \sum_{m=1}^z [S_m^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi S_m) + 10]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-5.12,5.12]	0
$F_{10}(S) = -20 \exp(-0.2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{z} \sum_{m=1}^z S_m^2}) - \exp(\frac{1}{z} \sum_{m=1}^z \cos(2\pi S_m)) + 20 + d$	(10,30,50,100)	[-32,32]	0
$F_{11}(S) = 1 + \sum_{m=1}^z \frac{S_m}{4000} - \prod_{m=1}^z \cos \frac{S_m}{\sqrt{m}}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-600, 600]	0

$F_{12}(S) = \frac{\pi}{z} \left\{ 10 \sin(\pi \tau_1) + \sum_{m=1}^{z-1} (\tau_m - 1)^2 [1 + 10 \sin^2(\pi \tau_{m+1}) + (\tau_2 - 1)^2] + \sum_{m=1}^z u(S_m, 10, 100, 4) \right\}$ $\tau_m = 1 + \frac{S_m + 1}{4}$ $u(S_m, b, x, i) = \begin{cases} x(S_m - b)^i & S_m > b \\ 0 & -b < S_m < b \\ x(-S_m - b)^i & S_m < -b \end{cases}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-50,50]	0
$F_{13}(S) = 0.1 \{ \sin^2(3\pi S_m) + \sum_{m=1}^z (S_m - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2(3\pi S_m + 1)] + (x_2 - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2 2\pi S_2] \}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-50,50]	0

Functions	Dimensions	Range	f_{min}
$F_{14}(S) = \left[\frac{1}{3000} + \sum_{m=1}^z \frac{1}{5 + \sum_{n=1}^m \frac{1}{(m-n+1)^2}} \right]^{-1}$	2	[-65.536, 65.536]	1
$F_{15}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^{11} \left[b_m - \frac{S_m (a_m + 2m S_m)}{a_m^2 + m^2 + S_m^2} \right]^2$	4	[-5, 5]	0.00030
$F_{16}(S) = 4S_1^2 - 2.1S_1^4 + \frac{1}{5}S_1^6 + S_1 S_2 - 4S_2^2 + 4S_2^4$	2	[-5, 5]	-1.0316
$F_{17}(S) = (S_2 - \frac{5.1}{482}S_1^2 + \frac{5}{97}S_1 - 6)^2 + 10 / (1 + \frac{1}{89}) \cos S_1 + 10$	2	[-5, 5]	0.398
$F_{18}(S) = [1 + (S_1 + S_2 + 1)^2 (19 - 14 S_1 + 3S_1^2 - 14 S_2 + 6S_2 S_1 + 3 S_2^2)] \times [30 - (2S_1 - 3S_2)^2 (18 - 32S_1 + 12 S_1^2 + 48S_2 - 36S_2 S_1 + 27 S_2^2)]$	2	[-2,2]	3
$F_{19}(S) = -\sum_{m=1}^4 d_m \exp(-\sum_{n=1}^m S_{mn} (S_m - q_{mn}))$	3	[1, 3]	-3.32
$F_{20}(S) = -\sum_{m=1}^4 d_m \exp(-\sum_{n=1}^6 S_{mn} (S_m - q_{mn}))$	6	[0, 1]	-3.32
$F_{21}(S) = -\sum_{m=1}^9 [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0,10]	-10.1532
$F_{22}(S) = -\sum_{m=1}^9 [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0, 10]	-10.4028
$F_{23}(S) = -\sum_{m=1}^9 [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0, 10]	-10.5363

Results and Discussion:

The SCSO algorithm is implemented for each problem, and its results are compared with those obtained from other hybridization algorithms.

Function	Original	Purpose
F1	0	5.98E+03
F2	0	3.84E+01
F3	0	1.02E+04
F4	0	2.73E+01
F5	28.800247	2.58E+06
F6	2.228888	6.08E+03
F7	0.000115	1.02E+00
F8	-7064.684071	-3.63E+03
F9	0	2.08E+02
F10	0	1.30E+01
F11	0	4.88E+01
F12	0.179116	1.12E+04
F13	2.287431	1.94E+06
F14	2.982105	1.04E+00
F15	0.000307	1.59E-03
F16	-1.031628	-1.03E+00
F17	0.397887	4.01E-01
F18	3.000008	3.01E+00
F19	-3.861573	-3.39E+00
F20	-3.136492	-3.01E+00

Conclusion:

The Sand Cat Swarm Optimization (SCSO) algorithm is inspired by the hunting behaviors, of sand cats. Effectively balances exploration and exploitation in optimization problems. It enhances performance by adapting movement strategies, reducing local optima entrapment, and improving convergence speed. Integrating hybrid techniques like PSO further refines its efficiency, making it a robust metaheuristic for complex problem-solving. The result is original function better than hybridization.

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